

PROBLEMS WITH THE FORMATION OF DISSERTATION FUNDS IN SCIENTIFIC LIBRARIES

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Annotation. Abstract. The article discusses the problems associated with the formation and organization of dissertation funds in scientific libraries. Special attention is paid to the issues of acquisition, storage, and accessibility of dissertation materials as unique sources of scientific knowledge. The role of modern information technologies in improving the system of collection, preservation, and use of dissertation works is analyzed. The article also proposes ways to optimize the management of dissertation funds in order to ensure their effective functioning as an integral part of scientific information resources.

Keywords: dissertation funds, scientific libraries, acquisition, access, electronic resources, information technologies, scientific information resources.

Recently, the use of electronic products and access to the Internet, including in the scientific world, has become a matter of course.

Many scientific libraries pride themselves on having the largest collections, but this may no longer be a significant advantage if the collections are not updated and new information technologies are not used. It is possible that in the near future, libraries will differ not in the volume of their collections, but in their ability to access information, the quality of their local databases, and the speed, completeness, and accuracy with which they can meet information requests, i.e., the quality of their information services as a whole. This is also true for the backgrounds of dissertations. Traditional forms of reader service have reached their limits. The rapid development of computer technology has made it more preferable for dissertations to be digitized and stored in machine-readable form, making them accessible to remote readers.

Projects in this area are being implemented in dozens of countries around the world using the most advanced technologies, and their experience is of great interest to the creators of electronic libraries in the CIS. One of the well-known foreign projects is the commercial project of providing access to electronic dissertations by UMI in Bell and Howell Information and Learning [1, b.7].

The UMI Dissertation Abstracts database contains about 2 million dissertations, of which the full texts (more than 450 thousand) are presented in PDF format. UMI's interaction with universities, which are the main suppliers of dissertations, follows the following pattern: dissertations are sent by universities to UMI in word processor format, and UMI creates a PDF file and a description of the dissertation.

Among the non-profit organizations, it is worth mentioning the international project **Networked Digital Library of Thesis and Dissertations** (NDLTD). Established in the mid-1990s as a cooperative project among American universities, it has rapidly expanded to an international level. NDLTD is an international federation that brings together 1,496 members from various countries around the world. The majority of NDLTD's members are universities, with a significant presence from the United States. Additionally, there are libraries and associations representing multiple

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organizations, such as OCLC and OhioLink. The purpose of this system is to support the indexing, archiving, distribution, and processing of electronic dissertations worldwide. At the same time, NDLTD supports the development of library technologies and tools for electronic databases.

Another interesting EBD project is **DissOnline** ("Dissertations online"). It has been developing in Germany since 1997. The objective of the project is to create full-text databases of dissertations that are being prepared at German universities. Universities (73) and the National Library of Germany, the coordinating body (center) of DissOnline, participate in the project. By receiving notifications of electronic dissertations and metadata from universities, it archives them and makes them available online. Similar projects are being developed in other countries, such as two university projects in France, one of which has become international, as well as projects in Australia, Spain, Switzerland, Finland, the United Kingdom, and Latin America and Africa [3, b.92].

The Russian State Library's "**Electronic Library of Dissertations**" project has been registered on the UNESCO website and deserves special attention.

The Russian State Library, which is the only repository of original dissertations defended in the country since 1944 in all fields except medicine and pharmacy, has a collection of over 800,000 dissertations. The project to create an electronic library of dissertations (ELD) has been developing since 2001.

It is supported by the Russian Foundation for Basic Research and is also funded from the RSL budget. The formation of the EDB is carried out in four directions: transfer of electronic versions of dissertations and abstracts by authors with the conclusion of a contract; transfer of electronic versions of dissertations and abstracts by organizations (libraries, universities, etc.); borrowing electronic versions of dissertations and abstracts from other electronic libraries under contracts with the holders of these libraries; scanning of the texts of dissertations and abstracts from the RSL collection [2, b.236].

As experience has shown, scanning the texts of dissertations is the most productive source of EDB acquisition. The library's dissertation department compiles lists and selects documents for transmission to a scanning organization. This work is carried out by ProSoft-M, one of the leading Russian companies specializing in converting large amounts of information into electronic form. It is worth noting that the library places great emphasis on the quality of scanning, as it is no secret that this method of creating an electronic copy has a high percentage of errors and shortcomings.

Readers who use the RSL EDB are divided into two categories: internal (through the RSL reading rooms) and external.

Currently, visitors to the reading rooms of the largest national libraries in Azerbaijan, Armenia, Georgia, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Moldova, Tajikistan, and Uzbekistan have the opportunity to use the electronic database of dissertations from the Russian State Library in their work. The project "Virtual Reading Rooms of the Electronic Library of Dissertations in the National Libraries of the CIS Countries" provides access to the electronic database of dissertations from the Russian State Library for the national libraries of these countries. The project was implemented by the Russian State Library with the support of the Interstate Fund for Humanitarian Cooperation of the CIS Member States. The project involves 9 libraries from 8 Commonwealth countries, and it is planned to increase the number of libraries connected to the electronic database in the future. The National Library is connected to the virtual electronic database of dissertations at the Russian State Library, which contains 900,000 electronic dissertations.

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In Uzbekistan, major libraries such as the National Library of the Republic of Uzbekistan named after A. Navoi, the Fundamental Library of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the State Scientific Medical Library, the Scientific Library of the National State University, and the Scientific Pedagogical Library have rich collections of dissertations by Uzbek scientists.

National Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan named after Alisher Navoi maintains a fund of 14,000 dissertations in various fields of knowledge in Russian and Uzbek. The material is arranged chronologically, starting in 1991. Since 1999, the library has been creating electronic databases of dissertations and abstracts of dissertations defended in Uzbekistan. Full-text electronic resources by the first quarter of 2023 amounted to 860,230 thousand units [4, b.84].

The full-text database of dissertations and abstracts is 15.5 thousand. Since 2004, at the National Bank named after Alisher Navoi was entrusted with the functions of storing dissertations defended in the republic, and from that period she began to create an electronic database of abstracts stored in the library. This work is carried out jointly with the Higher Attestation Commission (HAC) of the republic and makes it possible to present in an electronic environment a collection of abstracts and abstracts of dissertations defended in Uzbekistan in recent years. The library also maintains a catalog of electronic copies of dissertation works, which accounts for 90% of the collection. The library also provides electronic access to its dissertation catalogs via the Internet at www.natlib.uz.

The library's service system, organization, and determination of priority forms and methods of work must constantly respond to changes in users' information needs. To this end, readers have access to electronic databases, the ability to work with Internet resources, and a specialized room for working with dissertation collections (approximately 1,200 users per year). Many dissertations in the field of medicine that were defended before 2003 have been transferred to the State Medical Library of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Since 2004, works have once again begun to be submitted to the A. Navoi National Library.

The A. Navoi National Library of Uzbekistan, together with universities, conducts research to determine the demand for scientific and educational information, which has shown that information on economics, information technology, social sciences, and medicine is in the highest demand. The library is working on selecting the most frequently requested dissertations and creating a separate database for use in the library's local network.

The Fundamental Library of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan (FBAN RUz) is also rich in a fund of dissertations on various branches of knowledge defended by dissertators of the Academy of Sciences, which totals 7,932 copies. - dissertations, 65075 copies. - abstracts. All of them are reflected in the electronic catalog of the library, as well as in the printed catalog of dissertations available in the fund of the Fundamental Library of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Today, libraries face many challenges in the formation of their collections, including a lack of funding, technological difficulties in acquisition, and the destruction of the national system of depository storage and mandatory copies. These changes have had a significant impact on the information support for scientists and professionals. Recognizing the importance of Uzbekistan's integration into the global information system and the development of an information society in the country, it is crucial to strengthen cooperation with foreign partners and leverage the experience of libraries in other countries in managing their dissertation collections.

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